

Antibiotic Stewardship is an Urge of Every Healthcare Setup in This Era: Emerging Role of Physician, Pharmacist and Other Healthcare Providers.

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Article Details

ABSTRACT

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The Antibiotic Stewardship Program (ASP) is very important aspect and can play a potential role in health care setups specifically in hospitals. Due to increased unnecessary use of broad-spectrum antibiotics in an in-patients and ambulatory patients that can cause severe health-related problems including, drug resistance, increased cost of antibiotics. The main objective of this program is to determine the medical errors in patients' profile specifically medication charts contain antibiotics. The medication errors like wrong or improper dose, improper drug, improper time duration of antibiotic therapy, detect inappropriateness of antibiotics, especially broad spectrum, and determine the increasing cost of drugs in hospital stay. It is concluded in many research studies that through the implantation of ASP (Antibiotic Stewardship Program) irrational use of antibiotics can be controlled either at small clinics or in large tertiary care hospitals that is the only tool to lower the cost of therapy and protect patients from drug resistance so it should be adopted in all hospitals to reduce the health-related problems and save the money.

Figure 1. Graphical Abstract

INTRODUCTION:

BACKGROUND

Antibiotics:

The word antibiotic is derived from the Greek language which is comprised of two words i.e.-(Anti + Bios, anti means “against” and bios-means” life”). This is a term that was formerly defined as “the drug produced by fungi, bacteria, and other different microorganisms like actinomycetes and can control/inhibit the growth of other microorganisms,(Brunton & Knollmann, 2023) but when antibiotics may be produced in another way like in laboratories, so after scientists are going to define the term antibiotics as “the group of medicaments either is produced naturally or synthetically which can destroy, kill or stop, control the multiplication (growth) of microorganism causing infections. Antibiotics are the drugs that are usually used to treat infections.(Gk & Lewis, 2008)

From early decades as researchers came into being the definitions of antibiotics were changed from time to time as, in the year 1942 an English scientist WAKES MAN defined the term antibiotics as: “The material obtained from micro-organisms which is capable of inhibiting or killing the other microorganisms”, After that **Benedicts and Langlykke** who were considered great microbiologists, they were defined the term antibiotics in 1947 A.D. “A chemical composite which is produced either from living organism or it may produce synthetically and these substances in small concentration can inhibit or stop the growth processes of other kinds of a microorganism”. (Leonard, 1990)

Introduction:

In the light of above definitions, we can say that Antibiotics are agents that belong to the class of pharmaceuticals and are used either for prophylaxis or therapeutic purposes to treat infections.

In the early years of the 20th century, it was observed that most scientists worked on the discovery and development of more antibacterial drugs at that time antibiotics were helpful and useful to treat infections, but nowadays the situation become worse due to unauthorized and improper use of antibiotics, the most of the bacteria have become resistance from many antibiotics so this is not a little issue and not only issue for one country but that is big problem for whole world, due to that reason this is consider a world threat to human health by WHO.(WHO, 2018)

Antibiotics are the only substances that are used to treat various infections in humans and animals. They possess different properties like:

- Anti-microbial properties,
- Biological properties,
- Physiochemical properties have different mechanisms of action.(Dellit, 2007)

The statistical data and different studies proved that before two thousand sixteen A.D more than six thousand antibacterial agents were available but from that, about five thousand are produced by microorganisms. It is reported that from that no. i.e. 6000 entities only 300-400 antibacterial drugs are used for therapeutic purposes but the remaining are not effective or lethal.

It is also reported that annually almost 150 new chemical entities are included in that list, up to the year of 1960 A.D. mainly from Japan and most probably introduced from the United States of America.(Dellit, 2007; WHO, 2018)

ANTIBIOTIC STEWARDSHIP PROGRAM (ASP)

Introduction

"Antibiotic-stewardship program is a comprehensive and coordinated method by which the utilization of antimicrobial medications can be rationalized means improvement in appropriate treatment, reduction in antimicrobial resistance to treatment and best selection of drug for treating antimicrobial infection.(Pharmacy & Process, 2023)

In other words, we can define the ASP as either it is a program or process by which antibacterial drugs are

prescribed accurately, it means the physician should be bound to prescribe any antibiotics at the right dose (individualized dose) for patients according to age, body weight, renal function, and hypersensitivity issues (Dahar et al., 2026). Also, he or she is bound to prescribe the right scheduling/frequency for administration of antibiotic drugs to the patient, and also antibiotics must prescribe for proper and perfect time duration in response to certain antibacterial infections to achieve desirable clinical outcomes. It may be prescribed therapeutically, prophylactically, or empirically (Dager et al., 2018). Nowadays ASP considers a broad and advanced strategy to rationalize the use of antibiotics, and many researchers agree that this broad program/plan comprehensively has two goals i.e. primary goal and secondary goal (Dahar Raja et al., 2024).

The ASP mainly focused on patients' clinical outcomes and how they may be improved and the use of antibiotics minimized in such a way that as much as the desirable goal may be achieved in response to the selection of an accurate antibiotic drug to treat an infection for improvement of patient health (this is considered as a basic objective of successful ASP) (Paudyal et al., 2024). On another hand, the antibiotic stewardship program is engaged to decrease costs during the stay of patients in a hospital without compromising the quality of treatment (the second objective of ASP). (Dellit et al., 2007)

The advantages of this program;

- A. Limit the antimicrobial resistance against specified micro-organisms
- B. Reduces the side effects of treatment
- C. Limit the multiple antimicrobial resistance
- D. Limit the inappropriate prescriptions. (Bouwman-Boer, 2015; Wylegała et al., 2023)

Antibiotic stewardship has multiple objectives, to increase the quality of patient treatment by having antibiotic therapy and receiving medicines without any clinical evidence for inappropriate duration for specific infection therapy (Stoll & Weidmann, 2024). ASP finds the patterns of resistance and controls the multiple treatments for the patients who are receiving antibiotics, in this way, side effects and toxic effects can also be reduced (Matuluko et al., 2020). From many studies, it is established that unwanted and unusual use of antibiotics will increase resistance from specific species, and multiple drug treatments, which will lead to high costs of therapy (“Ten Golden Rules for Optimal Antibiotic Use in Hospital Settings: The WARNING Call to Action,” 2023). Many scholars studied that the increasing and unwanted use of antibiotics leads to high resistance (C.-N. Wang et al., 2020), by using this in all hospitals, and clinics will reduce misuse of antibiotics, and increase health quality and treatment that will decrease the antimicrobial resistance towards therapy. (Fong et al., 2018)

ASP is a program that provides a way to bind to all clinicians they should write antibiotics as per antibiotic guidelines and in this way the patients will saved from poly-therapy and increased costs as well (Sallam, 2024). So, this program is most important for all healthcare setups (Rendrayani et al., 2022). Due to this, WHO recognized and declared this a risk threat, so to limit the inappropriate utilization of therapy in all healthcare facilities antibiotics, these developing programs should be followed (Dixon et al., 2023; Shetty et al., 2024).

Historical Background:

An antibiotic stewardship program ASP is an organization program and systematic effort to educate and motivate the prescribers to prescribe any antibiotic drug without any doubt and to persuade prescribers to prescribe an evidence-based therapy either it may be empiric, prophylactic, or maybe therapeutic purposes, for order to control over and misuse antibiotics. Nowadays in developed societies, ASP is an organized effort of health professionals who are specialized in infectious –diseases (I-D) (Binda et al., 2020).

In the early days of 1940 great scientist Alexander Fleming recognized the resistance issue on behalf of the excess use of penicillin and remarked that its overuse would be a cause of the low effectiveness of antibiotics (Tan & Tatsumura, 2015), but this issue was ignored for a long time then in 1966 Canadian government recognized the importance of this and began reviewing antibiotic utilization and published this study in 1968, results showed 50% misuse of antibiotics (Reimann & D'Ambola, 1968; Ruedy, 1966).

At the start of 1970, hospitals in America implemented two main health-related programs, the first one was reviewing antibiotics therapy and the second one was the development of clinical pharmacy. That evaluation shows that there are 30% medication errors in medical wards and 63% errors in surgical wards.

Due to the increased ratio of drug resistance, researchers engaged to discover new entities, finally in the 1980s one class named cephalosporins was introduced, on other hand to control the use of antibiotics one program was launched that was “Hospital Infection Control Program “and that program was specially implemented to establish check and balance on antibiotic use organizationally (Schollenberg et al., 2018; Schollenberg & Albritton, 1980).

Furthermore, in a decade of 1990s in hospitals in the USA one program was introduced that consisted of different health professionals and that was self-control in terms of policies, procedures, and implementation organizationally to follow antibiotic guidelines in health care facilities. In 2013 ASP was implemented as compulsory in hospitals. In the year of 1996 John Gowan and Dale Gerding (they have a specialty on clostridium difficile from Emory University School Of Medicine), suggested “well-controlled trials of antimicrobials use on large scale and regulation employing erudite epidemiologic methods and precise to determine the best methods to prevent antimicrobial resistance and assure the proper and perfect use of antibiotics either they can prescribe empirically, prophylactically, or therapeutically in the regard of proper dose, frequency, and time period (Solomkin et al., 2003)

Later in 1997 one publication was published by the Infection Disease Society of America to control microbial resistance from different microorganisms and advise to government to implement ASP for appropriate antibiotic use that will help to prevent the emergence of resistance (Dellit et al., 2007).

After 1997 exactly ten years in 2007, certain types of microbial resistance increased to a high degree so the World Organization forced the world to implement ASP (Patel et al., 2007).

In the year of 2014, the CDC issued guidelines for all hospitals that they must establish this program in their hospitals, and in 2015 accepted and implemented ASP for all hospitals ASP must consist of a specialized team of infective diseases physicians, pharmacists, nurses, and microbiologist and they should fully authorize to make programs, policies, and procedures to make optimum utilization of antibiotics (N. C. for E. and Z. I. D. (U. S.). D. of H. Q. Promotion., 3 C.E.; Siegel et al., 2007)

Figure 2. Historical Background (Browne et al., 2020)

Advantages of ASP

There are a lot of advantages of that program some are discussed below. Optimum use of antibiotics has proved to following advantages: (“Policy Statement on Antimicrobial Stewardship by the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA), the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA), and the Pediatric Infectious Diseases Society (PIDS).,” 2012)

Increase quality of health care, especially health clinical improvements of patients.

Decrease ADRs like hypersensitivity, renal injury, and Hepatotoxicity.

Decreases drug-related problems like drug induce hepatitis etc.

Reduces excessive burden of money in hospitals during hospitality which is associated with antibiotics use.

Control microbial resistance.

Where ASP May Implemented:

This program must be established and implemented wherever antibiotics are prescribed for patients in healthcare facilities so we can control from this issue which is world threat.

Composition/Framework of ASP

The ASP is a teamwork of health professionals who are working in a healthcare setup, and it is organized by the ASP committee to develop a check and balance on the antibiotic prescribing and dispensing process. It consists of clinicians/physicians, clinical pharmacists, nurses, microbiologists, and epidemiologists one representative from the administration department, and a quality improvement specialist.

It is better that the ASP committee should meet once a month to overview the problems and share these with higher management for further development and implementation of effective ASP.[New_Antimicrobial_Stewardship_Standard (<https://www.jointcommission.org/assets>)

What Are Desirable Goals of ASP

There are multiple goals for ASP to achieve which are discussed below:

An effective ASP engaged to implement such an environment in which “an appropriate and optimum” use of antibiotics can be established

ASP should implement such a policy that all antibiotics are prescribed in individualized doses for patients to treat certain microbial infections versus C/S-directed antibiotic treatment.

ASP should establish treatment guidelines for clinicians and also provide feedback process in the sense of continuous education.

ASP should make a policy to survey the knowledge of every prescriber about antibiotics.

ASP organizes education programs on antibiotics, and infection treatment / clinical problems.

ASP helps to IT department to develop software that has to facility automatic stop orders to assist in making duration more visible to in-patient pharmacists as well as clinicians.(Newland et al., 2014; Newland & Hersh, 2010)

Figure 3. Summary of desirable Goals Of ASP

3. What kind Of Interventions on antibiotics prescribing

The main function of ASP is to find out the needs of the prescriber, provide all possible facilities to prescribe drugs for patients especially antibiotics accurately, and then establish a system of how antibiotics are prescribed either as per policies and protocols or not. An important work of core members of the ASP committee ((physician, pharmacist) to review the patient's medication profile for the following interventions:

Selection of an antibiotic against C/S report.

Antibiotics are prescribed to the patient at appropriate doses, especially in pads, and neonates, as per body weight, and renal and hepatic function accordingly.

Dose should be prescribed in metric systems like ml, mg, g, etc

Antibiotics are prescribed to patients as per standard dosing intervals according to dosage form/form of drug available

Selection of proper route of administration according to severity of infection and site of infection

Proper de-escalation of an antibiotic after culture results

If the above points are not followed by the prescriber then it is the responsibility of the ASP team to talk to those who may be involved, otherwise, report to the administration.(Cook & Gooch, 2015; Di Pentima & Chan, 2010).

These are the interventions but further tasks for core members of the ASP team:

Analyze patient's medication profile 74 hourly, monitor CS reports and clinical laboratory investigation values like Cr.Cl, LFTs, and CBC, etc. of the patients who are on antibiotic therapy, and advise to prescriber for an accurate time of antibiotics.(Zou et al., 2015)

Make monthly, and annual, reports of the progress of ASP concerning quality health care and saved costs and forward them to administration accordingly.(Newland et al., 2012)

Out Comes to Measure ASP

What are the outcomes that can be measured, from some Physician's (I-D) studies it is extracted that the following degree circumstances should be checked by ASP?

Annually cost of hospital pharmacy, related to procurement of antibiotics

Cost per patient on therapy of antibiotics

Evaluate compatibilities and incompatibilities among different antibiotics in the patient medication charts.

Conversion of the route of administration from I/V to PO

Intervene about ADRs, and dosages to individualize doses for patients

Report and decide to stop extra drugs in a patient's medication chart. (Morris et al., 2012; Reinwald et al., 2018).

5. Controversies about ASP

There are some controversies regarding the use of antibiotics, how can be measured? But scholars suggesting that and also well-known health organizations of the world mentioned that:

There are two ways to measure the units of usage of antibiotics consumed, either by "Day Of Therapy (DOT) or it can be measure by Defined Daily Doses (DDD). The latter method is most probably utilized all over Europe and other developed countries of the world.

The proper measurement of doses prescribed by physicians can be achieved by electronic administration record (eMAR), the basic data source for this regard. It is very tough to evaluate, due to some orders, on hold, that will oppose accounting data.

At this time the best way to measure these matters is the pre-approval method to get approval for antibiotics use from the I-D team.

It is hard to analyze the syndrome and specific drug for intervening, and preventing, and it is very difficult to change the routine habit of a clinician/prescriber to intervene in the drug which is prescribed earlier (Morris et al., 2012).

The Importance Of ASP

The ASP is a strategy that may implement such an organization as like, correct and optimum use of drugs especially antibiotic agents, to plan how life-threatening infections may be readily treated, and other medical advancements in usage and research regarding antibiotics in an organization.(Dellinger et al., 2013). According to some scholars there is in only USA 20% -50% of all antibiotics prescribed to treat infections in multiple hospitals that's are either unnecessary or inappropriate (Camins et al., 2009; Ingram et al., 2012), but the problem is that all drugs contain serious ADRs specially antibiotic drugs containing side effects as well as serious interactions, like antibiotic-associated diarrhea (Boggs et al., 2011; Lapi et al., 2012; Reinwald et al., 2018), so there must be implementation of antibiotic stewardship because not only in USA but in all over the world especially less developed countries there is large inappropriate antibiotic use and prescribed in high ratio without any authorized use, so these are the issues that are root causes of resistance developed by bacteria which is now declared world threat to health. (Huttner et al., 2013).

In this regard some organizations published and estimated that more than two million people are infected with antibiotic resistance due to the death ratio increasing in the USA up to 30,000/annually, so the government is making efforts to control antibiotic utilization because it is an important to control bacterial resistance as well as public safety from hazardous effects of drugs (CDC, 2019) (N. C. for E. and Z. I. D. (U. S.). D. of H. Q. P. D. of H. Q. Promotion., n.d.)

7. The Key Elements of ASP

The core elements of an ASP may be matched with guidelines of multiple organizations of world-developed countries, especially SHEA, ASHP, and JCI (Dellit, 2007)(Chukwu et al., 2024)(Mohammed et al., 2024).

Commitment of Leadership:

It is a very important aspect of an ASP as well as critical to implement a successful ASP organizationally. A good leader may proceed and implement ASP effectively and his commitment and dedication are also very important factors.

7.1.1 Leader:

It is the responsibility of the hospital

administrator or executive committee to select a leader/chairman (physician/clinician having specialization in infectious diseases) to lead ASP and who will be responsible for program outcomes because hospitals that have an ideal physician who leads to improve antibiotic use and have a large presence in patients care.(Srinivasan, 2011)

7.1.2 Co-Leader:

Selection of a person who leads in the absence of the leader or who will helpfully give advice to the leader for the implementation of an effective ASP in an organization, selection of a co-leader is also the responsibility of the hospital administrator or medical director. In this regard, a pharmacist who has a specialty in infectious diseases or antibiotics use is the best candidate, because he may help make reports of ASP as well as give the best choice to select antibiotics to treat a particular infection.(Rohde et al., 2013)

Accountability and Drug Expertise:

This is very important to make such forms for legal and non-verbal communication between staff of different departments like medical, surgical, pharmacy, and nursing as well as with administration also so it may contain several forms, including

- Duties and job descriptions related to ASP
- Monthly Annual performance/progress report
- CMEs related to ASP with participation from.

Rather than this in most large setup hospitals, PTC is not considered the ASP team in hospitals because it is not managing newly developed responsibilities and is bound to its formal duties like management of drug formulary, ADRs, etc (Ohl et al., 2011)(Cunha et al., 2013).

Staff That Supports ASP:

The role of the ASP head is increased in hospitals so it must work in co-ordination with other professionals. These are;

Physicians / Clinicians and Departmental Heads: -Physician a prescribers of drugs, so it should be energetic that clinicians should be fully involved in increasing the optimum use of antibiotic drugs (Edwards et al., 2011)

The nursing staff: They are the only one who can check that the sample for C/S may be taken before administration of the first dose of an antibiotic. Nurses should also be responsible to cross check medications daily and briefing the ASP team about patient conditions.(Cheng et al., 2009).

Laboratory Staff: - Staff of the microbiology lab should co-ordinate with the ASP team during their work, so that effective ASP is established. Beyond that laboratory staff can determine anti-bio gram. (Nathwani et al., 2019).

Quality Improvement Health professionals who are working in the quality improvement department can also play the role of maximizing antibiotic utilization according to the quality improvement process.(Amadeo et al., 2011).

Information Technology the IT department has the most important role in implementing ASP rules in hospitals, and clinical investigations and developing software to easily detect physician orders to control over use of antibiotics and manage antibiotic utilization details (Pestotnik, 2005).

7.4 Policies Which Supports ASP:

As every program has its own rules and regulations on how it may be run, so ASP has also effective policies for the management of antibiotic-appropriate utilization;

Make documents for dose, duration TDM, there should be proper documentation for such policies that notify the proper drug's indication for how it will be used, at what dose, and how much time because all antibiotics contain proper time duration to treat an infection, and availability of such policy indicated that either ASP effectively implemented or not, and making all information which helps modifications according to patient requirement (Edwards et al., 2011).

Development/Implementation of Facility Recommendation for Specific Treatment: This policy may facilitate proper treatment recommendations for certain infections like hospital-acquired pneumonia, UTI, etc. or it can be based on certain national and international guidelines.(Morris et al., 2010).

Interventions to Improvement Use of Antibiotics

At the pharmacist's desk making an intervention form to intervene in physician prescribing orders is the best tool to make a check and balance, but pharmacists monitor carefully that interventions should be according to recommended and authorized references, but these interventions should be according to available facilities, medicines, and physicians.

Broad Interventions:

Initially, the prescriber may prescribe large antibiotics on an empiric basis i.e. only for 48 – 72 hrs. to hospitalized patients up to the initial report/result of diagnostic information can be obtained from the laboratory. Broad Intervention contains three main intervention types time out of antibiotics, preauthorization, audit, and feedback.

Antibiotic's time out: -About Time out Antibiotics, stimulate reassessment of the requirement of antibiotics when a clear picture of infection comes into being, and more diagnostic information is available, but it is most important that all prescribed orders should be checked every 48-72 hours and some considerations should be observed that:

Is the patient's infection responding to a certain antibiotic or not? (Bornard et al., 2011)

Either antibiotic is prescribed at the right dose, right duration of time, and a patient receives with a correct route of administration.(S. Wang et al., 2015)

And an important to evaluate/check the physician's note that an antibiotic is prescribed for how much long? (Kaye, 2012)

Pre-Authorization of certain antibiotics for prescribing: In a few hospitals' antibiotics are categorized in a restricted category so it this very important to know how preauthorization can be taken from I-D consultants and it will require high expertise in the use of antibiotics organizationally (Dancer et al., 2013).

Audit and Feedback: It should be conducted by a particular staff team they have not been involved in the prescribing/treating team. Their teams consist of experts from internal or external sources. In this regard, other important interventions are spotted in the ASP.(Baur et al., 2017)

Pharmacy Determined Interventions

Route Of Administration (I/V to PO): As such I/V route requires technical issues as well and there are more chances of other infections on the other hand some antibiotics have good bioavailability like trimethoprim, Fluoroquinolones, linezolid, etc. so it is important when the patient becomes stable the antibiotic route should be changed from I/V to PO which can improve the safety of patients as well as decrease cost from unwanted dosage forms (Di Pentima & Chan, 2010)(Walsh et al., 2016)

Dose Adjustment of Antibiotics: The dose adjustment is required in case of dysfunction of organs like the kidney and liver, in that situation dose of a patient should be adjusted according to Cr. Cl, and LFTs respectively (McCallum et al., 2013).

Dose Optimizing of Antibiotics: Antibiotics should be used at optimum doses for specialized patients (renal compromised) this is based on therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM), maximizing treatment need for resistant bacteria, and for penetrating in CNS, etc (Cantón & Bryan, 2012a).

Duplication Therapy Alerts: There should be alerts to indicate multiple or duplicate therapies, related to overlapped spectrum of micro-organisms (Cantón & Bryan, 2012b).

Automatic stop Physician's Orders: This type of intervention is specified for prescribing orders especially when antibiotics are prescribed for surgical prophylaxis. So, it should be system facilitations that automatically stop that orders that will make duplicate, or increase the duration of the drug.

Interaction-Related Interventions: This is concerned with different types of interactions of antibiotics like Drug-Drug interactions, Drug –Food interactions, etc.(Gómez et al., 2006)

7.5.3 Interventions Specific for Infection and Syndrome:

These types of changes are related to increased prescription for particular infections, these interventions do not apply to effective therapy like sepsis, etc.

Many studies proved that empiric therapy of methicillin-resistant staphylococcus aureus infection should be stopped and according to the C/S report antibiotic therapy can be started because if empiric therapy continues there are more chances to resistance of certain microbial resistance (Gómez et al., 2006)(Di Pentima & Chan, 2010)(Dahar et al., 2021)

The patients on therapy for clostridium difficile infection and diagnosis identified that the patient has that infection, in that situation, the unnecessary antibiotics should be stopped, and the patient's medication chart should be reviewed after every required time (Johannsson et al., 2012)(Ostrowsky et al., 2013).

As for infection of community pneumonia pharmacy-related interventions have much more importance and that is focused on corrected recognizing problems in the current therapy of the patients. It needs:

Improved the accuracy of diagnosis

Follow the C/S report accordingly

The duration of therapy should be optimized (Caterino & Stevenson, 2012) (Bosso & Drew, 2011).

Other than these infections, some more critical infections need more concentration from the pharmacist desk, (like urinary tract infections, skin, and soft tissue infections, and certain abdominal infections) it should be ensured that patients who have these types of infections should not use overly broad-spectrum antibiotics and there is need of proper and perfect duration of antibiotic therapy also (Arcenillas et al., 2018) (Hooton et al., 2010)(Stevens et al., 2005).

System for Tracking and Reporting the Usage of Antibiotics

In every organization, there should be an effective system to report the usage of antibiotics and how these may be prescribed or dispensed. The following parameters should be implemented for the implementation of effective ASP.(Stevens et al., 2005)

7.6.1 Evaluation of prescribing trends of antibiotics:

In this regard only, measurement that is critical identifications and assessments to improve and implementing of policies to how the antibiotics should be prescribed for example either for prophylaxis, empiric or these may be prescribed for therapeutic purposes. Measurement may involve:

Policies should be followed as per expectations

Evaluation of patients' clinical outcomes

Measurement of the process of antibiotic usage

It may also include the evaluation of the prescribing process whether the prescriber prescribes antibiotics according to diagnostic criteria as per infection, and selection of a particular agent/drug as per recommendation, and whether that agent prescribes for a particular time or not (McQuillan et al., 2016)(“[Treatment guide for skin and soft tissue infections. Spanish Chemotherapy Society, Spanish Internal Medicine Society, Spanish Association of Surgeons].,” 2006).

Evaluation of Measures of the Use of Antibiotics

The measurement of the use of antibiotics is done in two ways that are proved by many studies either by “days of therapy (DOT) or “defined daily dose (DDD)”.

DOT is a system that is used to collect information about the utilization of antibiotics by patients during their hospital stay days for a patient admitted to the hospital taking 2 drugs, during his ten-day stay in the hospital the DOT of that patient will be 20.

DDD is a based on matric system that is used in hospitals where ASP is already implemented. It is an aggregation of total antibiotics utilized in grams by the patient during the hospital stay (Ohl et al., 2011)(Fridkin & Srinivasan, 2014). In addition to measuring the overall use of antibiotics in an organization/hospital, ASP also focuses on an analysis of specific antibiotics and locations where ASP is implemented. For Example, assessments of an intervention to improve the treatment community community-acquired pneumonia would be expected as the use of antibiotics in a general/medical ward rather than the surgical ward.(Polk et al., 2011)(Fridkin et al., 1999).

7.6.3 Evaluation of Clinical out Outcomes Measurement

For effective ASP to implement, it is most important that after tracking clinical outcomes these should be measured against organizational policies for betterment optimum use of antibiotic drugs, and this is also helpful for reducing antibiotic resistance.(McGowan, 2012)(Schulz et al., 2012). The development and spread of antibiotic resistance are multifactorial and studies assessing the impact of improved antibiotic use. The impact of interventions due to implementations of ASP on resistance is an example of best assessment when measurement will be focused on pathogens that are recovered from patients after hospitalization. There is Last but not least target of an ASP is cost saving during the hospitality of patients (Malani et al., 2013), and these costs which are saved due to the efforts of the ASP team will help in more development of ASP. After a starting period of cost saved, a pattern of usage of antibiotics, so there will be the chances to lower antibiotics utilization and cost may stabilize for some time. In that case, it is very important to support ASP to maintain the price of drugs.(Beardsley et al., 2012).

Training and Continuous Medical Education

Continuous Medical Education is the best tool to communicate and educate health professionals, so this is also the responsibility of the ASP team to share information regarding the use of antibiotics to motivate prescribing trends, and ASPs provide updates regarding prescribing, resistance, and disease management.(Camins et al., 2009).

The ways by which education can be provided for the use of antibiotics like:

Presentations on antibiotics

Posters

Through publications

Through Webinars and conferences.

Table 1. Summary of Key Points of Effective ASP

• The commitment of Leadership	There should be dedicated leadership i.e. physician and pharmacist, who will be responsible for implementing an effective ASP
• Accountability and drug expertise:	The leadership is bound to provide guidelines regarding the use of antibiotics to implement in an organization.
• Supporting staff:	To communicate with every supporting staff properly related to updating of use of antibiotics. One action must be taken by ASP leadership to implement at least one recommendation to evaluate the treatment period i.e. 48-72 hrs.
• Reporting and	There should be reporting of ASP either monthly or yearly

tracking:	that communicates with higher management about ASP progress.
• Continuous medical education:	The ASP team should plan to educate every health professional within an organization especially clinicians regarding resistance and maximize prescribing trends related to ASP

CHECKLIST TO EVALUATE KEY ELEMENTS OF ASP

This checklist is a proven way to check whether all aspects of ASP are implemented or not. And this is the way that assures that what actions should be taken? In developed hospitals, this is available systematically, but if there is ever no availability of such developed systems there is a need for a manual checklist it is very important to monitor the usage of antibiotics and this checklist may provide knowledge to staff to improve antibiotic utilization. As in Table 3.

Table 2. Checklist of Key Elements of ASP

Title	Description	Status	
Commitment of Leader and Co-Leader	Is there leader committed /dedicated or not for ASP activities		
	Either Co-leader helpful and al		
Accountability and Expertise	Are there written documents provided by leadership that related to support ASP like Job description, monthly or annually progress report, CME related forms etc	Y	N
	Is the Pharmacist working for improvement of ASP?	Y	N
Staff Supporting ASP (Are following staff support ASP organizationally?)	Prescribers' /Pharmacists/ Nurses	Y	N
	Quality Improving department	Y	N
	Laboratories	Y	N
	Information technology	Y	N
Policies Which Supports ASP	Is there any written policy for dose, duration, frequency for prescribing antibiotics? that facilitate to prescriber for prescribing antibiotics	Y	N
Specific Interventions To Improve ASP	Is there any system for review medication order of antibiotics after 48-72 hrs	Y	N
	Either Physician or pharmacist revises courses related to specific antibiotics use or not?	Y	N
	Automatic system of changing route of administration of an antibiotic therapy i.e. from I/V to P/O	Y	N
	Dose changes for specialized patients (organ dysfunction)	Y	N
	Is there any automatic alert to indicate duplication / unnecessary therapy	Y	N

Pharmacy Determined Interventions (Are the Following facilitation available)	Either prescribe enter note for sample for C/S prior prescribing antibiotics to treat certain infections i.e. CAP, UTI, CDI, etc or not?	Y	N
Specific Interventions related to infections	Either ASP measure documentation (duration, dose, indication?)	Y	N
	Either ASP monitor treatment recommendation or not?		
Evaluation And measuring ASP Efforts	Does ASP team report monthly ,yearly to management	Y	N
Tracking and reporting antibiotic use and outcomes	Does ASP share guidelines to prescriber	Y	N
	Have prescriber communicate about how they can improve their prescribing trends related to ASP	Y	N
Continuous Medical Education	give education to all health als related to use of	Y	N

Who Should Be the Team Member Of ASP?

ASP team consists of health professionals who are directly involved in the use of antibiotics for example: physicians, pharmacists, microbiologists, and nurses, who have a specialty in antibiotics/infection control / Infection diseases they may be a particular member of the ASP. From these team members, a physician who has specialized will be the leader/chairman of this program. He will be a consultant or faculty member at the hospital. One competent and qualified pharmacist who has also a specialty in infectious diseases may play the role of co-leader / co-chairman of this program, and other members from the micro-lab and nursing department should sit on the committee. The committee will decide on program policies to enhance the utilization of antibiotics in hospitals.(Pestotnik et al., 1996)(Phillips, 2001).

ANTIBIOTIC STEWARDSHIP TEAM

Figure 5: Mind map of ASP team members

JOB DESCRIPTION / ROLE OF INDIVIDUALS OF ASP TEAM MEMBERS

The Job Description for every team member of ASP will be decided by the hospital administrator or executive committee, but here there are generally discussions about the role and what the responsibilities of each member of ASP are:

I-D Physician

For the implementation of successful ASP, it is very important to select / present at least one I-D senior physician who should be dedicated to giving his time to designing ASP, supervising ASP, Implementing Policies of ASP (Sunenshine et al., 2004)

I-D Pharmacist / Clinical Pharmacist

In ASP from all other core team members, the pharmacist is the origin of ASP in the sense of drug specialist, management of antibiotics from dispensing to administration and saving in terms of cost.

A clinical pharmacist is a specialist in I-Ds have several responsibilities regarding ASP (Howard et al., 2001) like; making and developing policies for antibiotic use, educate all professionals in hospitals, review the Patient's medication charts which are on antibiotics therapy, research on program (ASP) outcomes (Kohn et al., 2000)

Microbiologist

A microbiologist from micro-lab is considered an important part of a successful ASP, he has will be responsible for; summarize data of patients who have microbial resistance and provide ASP, to determine the burden of resistance to antibiotics, help ASP to make decisions regarding drug, microbiologists are also helpful and prepare anti bio gram for specific patient care like patients in ICU, CCU, HDU, etc.(Stratton et al., 1993). He should also report ASP about the antibiotic susceptibility of microorganisms.(Trenholme et al., 1989).

7.1.4 I-D Nurse and representative of the epidemiology department.

There are many boulevards for collaboration among the I-C / nursing department and ASP. The nursing staff from the I-C department has highly needed data and details on infections which may help the ASP team to evaluate their outcome for the betterment of further strategies. Epidemiologists an expert in developing strategies to help ASP, so any ASP should be followed to achieve appropriate utilization of

antibiotics (Glenton et al., 2022).

Hospital Administrator

There is no meaning in the efforts of all team members of ASP without the support of the management of an organization where ASP going to be implemented. Without support from hospital administrators, program cannot be funded because the ASP program itself does not provide any revenue. So hospital administrators should be publically following ASP, for better and optimum use of antibiotics in a hospital.(Gonzales et al., 1999)(Graffunder et al., 2002).

Table 3. Key Responsibilities of ASP Team

I-D Physician	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing ASP, • Supervising ASP. • Implementing Policies of ASP
I-D Pharmacist / Clinical Pharmacist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making and developing policies for antibiotic use • Educate all professionals in hospitals • Review the Patient's medication charts which are on antibiotics therapy • Research on program (ASP) outcomes
Microbiologist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To summarize data of patients who have microbial resistance and provide ASP • To determine the burden of resistance to antibiotics • Help ASP to make decisions regarding drug
I-D Nurse and representative of the epidemiology department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The nursing staff from the I-C department has highly needed data and details on infections which may help the ASP team to evaluate their outcome for the betterment of further strategies and Epidemiologists an expert in developing strategies to help ASP, so any ASP should be followed to achieve appropriate utilization of antibiotics
Hospital Administrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issue Funds for ASP and overall monitoring for better and optimum use of antibiotics in a hospital

OBJECTIVES OF ASP

To determine the errors in medication charts of antibiotics of patients like improper dose, improper drug, improper duration

To detect the inappropriateness of antibiotics, especially broad spectrum.

To determine the increasing cost of drugs in hospital stay (Kaki et al., 2011) (Bauer et al., 2010).

SCOPE OF ASP

The improper / over usage of antibiotics is common in our society and all over the world and this problem

was declared as a large threat to public health by W.H.O.

ASP evaluates the common prescribing errors related to the therapy of antibacterial, i.e. Wrong medication to the wrong patients, improper selection of antimicrobials according to susceptible infective organisms, improper scheduling (time to take a dose of medicines), excess or improper duration of therapy, selection of incorrect route of administration of antibacterial, irrational use of large spectrum antibiotics, unauthorized use of antibiotics to increase the rationality of treatment and provide a way to limit the misuse and indicate and this study will help to promote the antibiotic stewardship organizationally.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that;

Among the less developed countries use of antibiotics is very illegal and unauthorized so prescription errors in which the highest ratio of “wrong frequency, improper dose (high and low doses), and unnecessary drugs prescribed “respectively like prescription errors may be involved.

These errors may lead to either toxicity of the drug or resistance from the susceptible microorganisms.

Many prescriptions were involved in which quality care was compromised in response to wrong prescribing trends related to antibiotics.

Improper and illegal use of antibiotics is a main cause of antimicrobial resistance So it should be controlled through proper implementation of ASP.

Recommendation from Authors

Antibiotic stewardship programs are very important for all healthcare organizations. It is proved from many research studies that the quality of patient health care increased and chances of bacterial resistance decreased due to optimum use and use of antibiotics perfectly which can only be achieved through high efforts of ASP team, and quantitatively. These types of protocols and their implementation will only be done by the upper management of the hospital with the coordination of all the healthcare staff. Moreover, by executing this program, we can save the cost of therapy and other health-related expenses. So, ASP should be implemented in all health care organizations and the government should recognize that issue and make a policy to control the illegal and inappropriate use of antibiotics through the Antibiotic Stewardship Program. The government should make strategies for the execution of above said program in all hospitals for cost-effective therapy particularly in resistant patients.

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AI Generative Statement

The author (s) of this study declared that AI wasn’t used to create this manuscript.

Abbreviations Used

ASP (antibiotic Stewardship Program), ME (medication Errors), ID (Infective Diseases), IC (Infection Control), TDM (Therapeutic Drug Monitoring), CBC (Complete Blood Count).

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